

Performance and Operational Characteristics of RAG vs MCP Knowledge Access Pipelines in Small LLM Environments

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Abstract

Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) has become the standard approach for augmenting LLM knowledge, yet high operational complexity and dependency on specialized personnel remain persistent challenges in production environments. Industry reports indicate that up to 70% of RAG systems fail to meet expectations in production, and 90% of agentic RAG projects failed in 2024. This study empirically investigates whether Model Context Protocol (MCP)-based pipelines can alleviate these operational burdens while achieving practical performance levels.

We compare two RAG variants (naive, tuned) and five MCP variants (plain, domain, parallel, chained, ontology) on 105 Docker documentation queries using Qwen 2.5 7B, Llama 3.1 8B, and Qwen 2.5 14B. Tuned RAG achieves the highest accuracy (75.0%), but the 46 percentage point gap from naive RAG (29.4%) reveals extreme configuration sensitivity. MCP parallel achieves 64.0% without any parameter tuning, while reducing tuning parameters from 9 to 2, failure points from 3 to 1, and eliminating external dependencies beyond the LLM itself. On 14B models, MCP domain (73.1%) outscored tuned RAG (66.7%), suggesting a possible tipping point as model capabilities improve, though this remains a preliminary observation requiring further validation.

Keywords: RAG, MCP, small LLM, operational complexity, technical debt, Docker, knowledge access pipeline

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) is the standard architecture for injecting external knowledge into LLMs, adopted in 30–60% of enterprise AI use cases. However, production deployment of RAG systems continues to exhibit high failure rates. Community feedback describes RAG as "still a fragile dance of glue code and faith" [12], while effective RAG implementation requires managing a complex technology stack including vector databases, retrievers, and orchestration layers, demanding highly mature engineering and DevOps practices [13]. Building a production-grade enterprise RAG system in-house can require a dedicated AI engineering team for 6–12 months or more [11].

This challenge intensifies in environments where specialized personnel are difficult to retain. RAG pipeline configuration values (chunk size, overlap, Top-K, embedding model, etc.) cannot be explained from code alone—they represent tacit knowledge derived through experimental trial and error. When responsible engineers depart, this tacit knowledge is lost, accumulating as organizational technical debt.

1.2 MCP as an Alternative

Model Context Protocol (MCP), proposed by Anthropic, is a standardized protocol enabling LLMs to access external tools and data sources in a structured manner. Unlike RAG, MCP requires neither embedding models nor vector databases, accessing knowledge through explicit tool-based logic. While RAG pipelines are tightly coupled to specific models and embedding strategies—requiring re-embedding of entire corpora when switching models—MCP is model agnostic [12].

This study explores MCP as an alternative to RAG's operational complexity. Our objective is to comprehensively compare not only performance but also tuning costs, personnel dependency, and failure recovery across both approaches.

1.3 Research Questions

RQ1. What level of performance does MCP-based knowledge access achieve compared to RAG in small LLM (7–8B) environments?

RQ2. What are the quantitative differences in operational complexity (configuration parameters, external dependencies, failure points, code readability) between RAG and MCP?

RQ3. How does pipeline performance change with increased model size (14B)?

2. Related Work

2.1 RAG: Progress and Operational Challenges

Since Lewis et al. (2020) introduced RAG [1], vector DB-based retrieval-generation pipelines have become the standard for LLM knowledge augmentation, with over 1,200 related papers on arXiv in 2024 alone. Various techniques have been proposed for improving RAG performance, including hybrid retrieval (combining dense and sparse search), reranking (cross-encoder-based result reordering), semantic chunking (meaning-unit segmentation), and parent-child chunks (hierarchical chunk structures). Self-RAG [4] introduced models that autonomously judge retrieval necessity, while Agentic RAG adopts multi-step retrieval strategies.

However, these techniques further increase RAG's operational complexity. A 2025 CDC policy RAG study [14] reported that naive fixed-size chunking achieved faithfulness scores of only 0.47–0.51, while optimized semantic chunking reached 0.79–0.82, with 80% of RAG failures traced to chunking decisions. Industry reports indicate that up to 70% of RAG systems fail to meet production expectations [11], and 90% of agentic RAG projects failed in production in 2024 [10]. In this study, we use tuned RAG without reranking or other advanced techniques as our baseline, reflecting the level of RAG commonly deployed in practice. This is an intentional design choice.

2.2 MCP and Tool-Based Knowledge Access

MCP is a standardized protocol for LLM interaction with external systems. Existing research typically distinguishes RAG as a tool "for knowing" and MCP as a tool "for doing." This study differentiates itself by directly comparing both approaches on identical knowledge access tasks.

3. Experimental Design

3.1 Pipeline Configuration

We compare seven pipelines spanning RAG and MCP variants. For MCP, we iteratively refined the design from an initial plain implementation through domain-specialized tools, parallel workers, and chaining, exploring optimal architectures at each stage.

Table 1. Experimental Pipeline Configuration

Pipeline	Method	Key Settings
naive RAG	Vector similarity search	Chunk 800, Top-5, nomic-embed-text
tuned RAG	Vector similarity search	Chunk 1200, Top-10, bge-m3
MCP plain	LLM tool calling	5 file exploration tools
MCP domain	LLM tool calling	6 domain tools, structured index
MCP parallel	Rule-based routing	4 parallel workers + keyword router
MCP chained	Rules + chaining	Inter-worker result linking, 2-stage
MCP+Ontology	LLM tool calling + KG	Ontology relation traversal

3.2 MCP Parallel Architecture

MCP parallel is the core architecture proposed in this study, eliminating the tool calling dependency of conventional MCP. Figure 1 illustrates the structural differences among RAG, conventional MCP, and MCP parallel.

Figure 1. Pipeline Architecture Comparison

Key differences: (1) A rule-based router classifies questions via keyword matching without LLM calls (routing time: 0–1ms). (2) Four independent workers (command, error, concept, config) search their respective structured indexes in parallel. (3) The LLM is called only once, performing the same role as in RAG: "read context and answer."

MCP parallel replaces LLM-based routing with deterministic routing while preserving MCP's core philosophy of structured knowledge access through domain-specific workers. The correspondence to MCP standard specifications is: (1) MCP Server tool definitions → per-worker structured indexes, (2) MCP Client tool invocation → router-to-worker dispatch, (3) structured tool responses → typed worker results. Only the routing agent changes (LLM → rules); the knowledge access structure itself follows MCP patterns. We position this as an MCP-inspired architecture.

3.3 Dataset and Environment

We collected 15 markdown documents across 7 categories from official Docker documentation and designed 105

evaluation questions (easy/medium/hard). As our goal is system-level pipeline behavior comparison rather than large-scale benchmarking, we prioritized category balance and difficulty distribution. All experiments were conducted on RTX 3080 Ti (12GB), AMD CPU, 62GB RAM using Ollama. Primary models: Qwen 2.5 7B (Q4_K_M) and Llama 3.1 8B (Q4_K_M); 14B reference: Qwen 2.5 14B (Q4_K_M).

Scoring used an LLM-as-Judge approach with 0–1 continuous scores, repeated 3 times per experiment. For scoring reliability, Qwen 7B Judge results were cross-validated with Llama 8B Judge (315 cases). Overall agreement rate was 70.5%, with relative pipeline rankings preserved identically across both judges (RAG < MCP < MCP+Ontology). Hallucination was defined as "generation of information not supported by retrieved documents or MCP tool responses."

4. Results

4.1 Overall Performance (RQ1)

Figure 2. Pipeline Accuracy Comparison (7-8B Models)

Table 2. Pipeline Performance (7-8B, 3-run average)

Pipeline	Qwen 7B	Llama 8B	Halluc.	Latency
naive RAG	29.4% ($\pm 0.2\%$)	34.0% ($\pm 1.6\%$)	$\leq 0.3\%$	1,240ms
tuned RAG	75.0% ($\pm 1.2\%$)	-	$\leq 0.3\%$	3,810ms
MCP plain	59.7% ($\pm 2.2\%$)	47.7% ($\pm 1.8\%$)	$\leq 0.3\%$	4,800ms
MCP domain	59.0%	-	$\leq 0.3\%$	5,100ms
MCP parallel	64.0% ($\pm 1.6\%$)	62.0% ($\pm 0.9\%$)	$\leq 0.3\%$	5,020ms
MCP+Ontology	61.5% ($\pm 2.1\%$)	57.2% ($\pm 1.3\%$)	$\leq 0.3\%$	4,824ms

Tuned RAG achieved the highest accuracy at 75.0%, with MCP parallel at 64.0% (11 pp gap). Tuned RAG represents a reasonably strong baseline commonly used in practical deployments, without reranking or semantic chunking; further techniques could improve RAG performance, as noted in our limitations. However, the 46 pp gap between naive RAG (29.4%) and tuned RAG (75.0%) occurred from configuration changes alone within the same RAG architecture, demonstrating extreme configuration sensitivity. MCP parallel achieved 64.0% without any parameter tuning.

Hallucination rates were $\leq 0.3\%$ across all pipelines. This is attributable to all pipelines being designed to generate answers solely from retrieved context, with explicit prompt instructions to not generate information absent from the context. The conservative hallucination criterion (generation of information unsupported by retrieved documents) means that inaccurate answers are reflected as low accuracy scores rather than being classified as hallucinations.

4.2 RAG Configuration Sensitivity

Figure 3. RAG Configuration Sensitivity vs MCP Baseline

Table 3. RAG Configuration Changes

Setting	naive RAG	tuned RAG	Change
Chunk size	800 chars	1,200 chars	+50%
Overlap	100 chars	200 chars	+100%
Top-K	5	10	+100%
Embedding model	nomic-embed-text	bge-m3	Model swap
Final accuracy	29.4%	75.0%	+45.6 pp

On the same documents, same questions, and same LLM, changing only RAG configuration values produced a 45.6 pp performance difference. These optimal values must be discovered through trial and error, and require re-tuning when domain or document characteristics change. When responsible personnel change, the rationale for "why chunk size is 1,200" or "why bge-m3" can be lost.

4.3 Judge Cross-Validation

Table 4. LLM-as-Judge Cross-Validation (Qwen 7B vs Llama 8B)

Pipeline	Qwen Judge	Llama Judge	Agreement
naive RAG	29.2%	35.5%	86.7%
MCP plain	62.5%	81.0%	66.7%
MCP+Ontology	60.0%	82.3%	58.1%
Overall	50.6%	66.3%	70.5%

Llama Judge systematically assigned higher scores to MCP variants (MCP: Qwen 62.5% vs Llama 81.0%). This indicates that the primary judge model (Qwen 7B) scores MCP conservatively, suggesting that MCP performance reported in this paper may represent a lower bound. Relative pipeline rankings (RAG < MCP < MCP+Ontology) were identically preserved across both judges, demonstrating that our comparative conclusions are robust to judge model selection.

4.4 Operational Complexity (RQ2)

Figure 4. Operational Complexity Radar Chart

Table 5. Operational Complexity Comparison

Metric	tuned RAG	MCP parallel
Code LOC (effective)	616 lines / 6 files	771 lines / 3 files
External dependencies	Embedding + VectorStore + LLM	LLM only
Tuning parameters	9 (experimental)	2 (rule-based)
Pre-tuning performance	29.4%	64.0% (no tuning needed)
Failure points	3 (embed/vector/LLM)	1 (LLM)
Config readability	Numeric values (tacit)	Rule logic (explicit)
Failure recovery	Vector index rebuild	LLM restart
Domain change	Re-embed + re-tune	Re-run parser

RAG's 9 tuning parameters (maxChunkSize, overlapSize, minChunkSize, topK, minScore, maxContextLength, embedding model, batchSize, temperature) are all experimentally determined values. MCP parallel's 2 parameters (maxTokens, relevance threshold) are rule-based with clear rationale in the code. From a failure point perspective, RAG depends on 3 independent components while MCP parallel has a single LLM dependency.

4.5 Model Size Effect (RQ3)

Figure 5. Model Size Effect: RAG vs MCP Performance

Table 6. 14B Experiment Results (Directional)

Pipeline	7B (Qwen)	14B (Qwen)	Change
tuned RAG	75.0%	66.7%	-8.3 pp
MCP domain	59.0%	73.1%	+14.1 pp

MCP domain (73.1%) outscored tuned RAG (66.7%) on the 14B model. The primary bottleneck for MCP at 7B—limited tool calling capability—appears to be alleviated at 14B. However, this experiment was conducted only once due to GPU resource constraints, and MCP domain results are from 36 questions (mid-run). The 14B model required 10.8GB/12GB VRAM at 349W, making continuous operation in commodity environments impractical. This is a preliminary observation that does not establish statistical significance and serves as motivation for future research.

4.6 Category Analysis

Figure 6. Category-wise Accuracy (Qwen 7B, original 3 pipelines)

The most dramatic category-level difference appeared in Dockerfile, where naive RAG scored 9.8% versus MCP+Ontology at 69.2% (59.4 pp gap). Large gaps were also observed in Container-lifecycle (48.6%→70.9%) and

Volume-storage (27.7%→61.9%).

5. Discussion

5.1 Performance–Operational Cost Trade-off

Our results demonstrate a clear trade-off between RAG and MCP. Tuned RAG achieves peak performance (75.0%) but requires experimental tuning of 9 parameters and operation of 3 external components. MCP parallel trails by 11 pp but achieves this without tuning through a single dependency (LLM only).

The acceptability of this trade-off depends on the operational environment. In high-availability environments, the difference between 3 and 1 failure points directly impacts operational stability, and the difference in recovery time (vector index rebuild vs. LLM restart) translates to service downtime.

5.2 Technical Debt and Personnel Dependency

RAG's 46 pp configuration sensitivity (29.4%→75.0%) represents not merely a performance gap but an operational risk. When the engineer who found the optimal configuration departs, the rationale for those settings is lost. Successors must repeat the same trial-and-error process, during which the system may operate at suboptimal settings. This was empirically demonstrated in our experiments, where identical codebases produced 2.5x performance differences through configuration changes alone.

MCP parallel's configuration consists of rule-based logic readable from code. "If the question contains 'volume', the volume worker handles it" is an explicit rule amenable to knowledge transfer. RAG's "chunk size 1200, Top-K 10, bge-m3" configuration values have no in-code rationale.

5.3 MCP Design Lessons

The four-iteration MCP redesign process in this study provides instructive findings. Transitioning from MCP plain (file exploration tools, 59.7%) to MCP domain (structured tools + tool calling, 59.0%) yielded no improvement due to 7B model tool calling limitations. MCP parallel (rule-based router, 64.0%) achieved its key improvement by removing tool calling and reducing LLM cognitive load to match RAG: "read and answer." MCP chained (worker chaining) failed to improve performance as additional context hindered the 7B model's ability to identify key information.

5.4 Model Evolution and Tipping Points

The MCP score exceeding RAG at 14B (73.1% vs 66.7%) suggests that model capability improvements raise MCP's performance ceiling. The primary bottlenecks for MCP at 7B—tool calling ability and long context processing—are areas that naturally improve with model development. However, 14B models require 10.8GB VRAM at 349W, making continuous commodity deployment impractical, reinforcing that 7–8B models remain the practical choice at present.

6. Limitations

(1) Single domain: Only Docker documentation was tested; cross-domain generalization requires further validation. (2) LLM-as-Judge bias: Cross-validation between Qwen 7B and Llama 8B judges showed 70.5% agreement; relative rankings were preserved but absolute score bias exists. No human evaluation was conducted. (3) 14B experiment: Only 1 run with partial data due to GPU constraints; no statistical significance established. (4) Question–tool design independence: Both the 105 evaluation questions and MCP tools were designed by the same research team. Questions were not modified after MCP tool design was complete, and questions were evenly distributed across 7 categories (15 each) to avoid bias toward specific workers; however, structural bias cannot be fully excluded, and future work should employ external benchmarks. (5) Scope of "no tuning": MCP parallel requires no parameter tuning, but initial design of keyword routers and workers requires domain knowledge. This design cost differs in nature from RAG tuning cost but is non-negligible. (6) RAG optimization scope: Advanced

techniques including reranking (bge-reranker, ColBERT), semantic chunking, and parent-child chunks were not applied; RAG with such techniques could achieve higher performance. (7) Operational metrics: LOC and parameter counts were reported, but cyclomatic complexity and actual failure recovery times were not measured.

7. Conclusion

This study empirically compared performance and operational characteristics of RAG and MCP knowledge access pipelines in small LLM environments. Key findings:

First, tuned RAG achieves peak performance (75.0%) but is extremely sensitive to configuration, with a 45.6 pp gap between naive and tuned configurations. This means RAG performance depends on tuning quality rather than architecture, carrying technical debt and personnel dependency risks in operational environments.

Second, MCP parallel achieves 64.0% without tuning, providing structural advantages including dependency elimination (LLM only), failure point reduction (3→1), and configuration readability. Where the 11 pp performance gap is acceptable, it constitutes a viable alternative for reducing operational complexity and technical debt.

Third, on 14B models, MCP scored higher than RAG (73.1% vs 66.7%), though this is a preliminary observation without statistical significance and serves as motivation for future research rather than an established finding.

Future work should extend these findings through multi-domain validation, human evaluation, RAG+MCP hybrid architecture exploration, and operational cost measurement (handover time, failure recovery time). In particular, comparison against stronger RAG baselines incorporating reranking and hybrid retrieval is essential.

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